

A NOVEL SLEEVE ASSEMBLY METHOD FOR SPM MOTORS USING CFRP WITH ATYPICAL LAYUP

Kazunori Takagaki, Ichiya Takahashi, Masami Kume, Tatsuya Koyama and Hiroki Kobayashi¹

¹ Composite & Ceramic Material Section, Materials & Processing Technology Department,
 Advanced Technology R&D Center, Mitsubishi Electric Corporation
 8-1-1, Tsukaguchi-Honmachi, Amagasaki City, Hyogo 661-8661, Japan
 Email: Takagaki.Kazunori@ak.MitsubishiElectric.co.jp
 web page: <https://www.mitsubishielectric.com/en/>

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ABSTRACT

Motor is one of the most important components for industry. Some of surface permanent magnet (SPM) motors have sleeves made of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRPs) to prevent magnets from separating during operation. Though the CFRP sleeve is conventionally assembled by press fitting, this process is cost intensive. Therefore, this research aimed to propose a novel sleeve assembly method for the SPM motors to reduce the cost and the press-fit pressure. For the purpose, a theoretical analysis based on the classical lamination theory was carried out and the concept of ‘anomalous Poisson’s effect’ was proposed. This is the coupling effect of an anisotropic material, inducing normal strain by shear force. The optimized layup was determined to maximize the tension in the circumferential direction after assembly. A CFRP cylinder was then fabricated to experimentally validate the theoretical result. Torsion test was carried out on the cylinder, successfully confirming the validity of the anomalous Poisson’s effect. In addition, a concept was proposed to prevent interaction between the cylinder and core during assembly.

1 INTRODUCTION

Motor is one of the most important components for industry. It is a key element for electric vehicles, factory automation and so on. Since motors consume more than 40% of global electricity consumption [1], improving their performance is a crucial issue for addressing global warming as well as for cost reduction.

Figure 1: Schematic of rotor of SPM motor with CFRP cylinder.

(a) Cross sectional view of whole structure. (b) Enlarged view of blue line in (a).

Core and magnets are press-fitted, inducing tension in CFRP. It prevents the magnet from leaving from the core under centrifugal force.

Surface permanent magnet (SPM) motors have magnets mounted on the rotor cores and are highly efficient. Figure 1 depicts schematic of a SPM motor. SPM motors with high-speed rotation use sleeves to prevent the magnets separating from the cores under the centrifugal force. Since high strength materials are desirable for the sleeve, carbon fibre reinforce plastic (CFRP) has been adopted for some of SPM motors. A CFRP cylinder is assembled onto the core by press-fitting, making the motor manufacturing process uneconomical. This research proposes a novel sleeve assembly process with CFRP having an atypical stacking sequence to reduce the cost and the press-fit pressure.

2 CONCEPT AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Basic Concept

Figure 2 illustrates the schematic of the conventional and proposed assembly processes. As shown in Figure 2 (a), the conventional method utilizes a CFRP with fibres mainly aligned in the circumferential (0°) direction. A core and magnets are press-fitted into a CFRP, inducing tension due to the change in the circumferential length of the CFRP. Meanwhile, the basic concept of the assembly process proposed in this research is to use a CFRP cylinder which expands in the radial direction when it is subjected to torsion. Torque generally do not affect diameters of cylinders made of isotropic materials (e.g., metals and polymers), and the same is true for even CFRP with a harmonic layup. The torsion-diameter coupling, however, is achieved by activating the coupling effect of an anisotropic material. Based on the analogy to the Poisson's effect, the phenomenon is called 'anomalous Poisson's effect' in this research. The middle image in Figure 2 (b) depicts the expanded CFRP under torque. After inserting the core and magnet into the expanded CFRP, the torque is released, and more preferably CFRP is twisted in the opposite direction to induce tension as shown in the bottom figure. This assembly method tightly holds the magnets in place while eliminating press-fitting process. The layup of the CFRP is discussed in the following section.

2.2 Theoretical analysis

For simplicity, CFRP with two fibre direction ($[\theta_1/\theta_2]_{2S}$) was considered in this research. Figure 3 illustrates the coordinate system used in this research. According to the classical lamination theory (CLT), resultant force is written as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\{\mathbf{N}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{M}\}$ are force and moment resultant with three dimensions, $[\mathbf{A}]$, $[\mathbf{B}]$, and $[\mathbf{D}]$ are 3x3 stiffness matrices, and $\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0\}$ and $\{\boldsymbol{\kappa}\}$ are neutral plane strains and curvatures with three dimensions. For specific derivation and values, see a reference [2] for example. This research deals with symmetric laminates and therefore does not consider bending moment. Thus, $[\mathbf{B}]$ and $[\mathbf{D}]$ matrices are ignored as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where ε^0 and γ^0 are normal and shear strains at the neutral plane. The subscripts x and y represent the directions of a laminate. Assuming that only torque is applied to the cylinder, shear force N_{xy} is solely induced and eq. (2) is transformed as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A]^{-1}_{11} & [A]^{-1}_{12} & [A]^{-1}_{16} \\ [A]^{-1}_{12} & [A]^{-1}_{22} & [A]^{-1}_{26} \\ [A]^{-1}_{16} & [A]^{-1}_{26} & [A]^{-1}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} [A]^{-1}_{16} \\ [A]^{-1}_{26} \\ [A]^{-1}_{66} \end{Bmatrix} N_{xy} \quad (3)$$

where $[A]^{-1}_{ij}$ indicates the $[i, j]$ component of the inverse matrix of the in-plane stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{A}]$.

Although several failure criteria exist [3], the maximum strain theory was adopted in this research due to its simplicity. Based on the theory, the maximum allowable shear force is shown as

$$N_{xy \max} = \min \left(\frac{Y_1^-}{\varepsilon_1^1}, \frac{Y_1^+}{\varepsilon_1^1}, \frac{Y_2^-}{\varepsilon_2^1}, \frac{Y_2^+}{\varepsilon_2^1}, \frac{Y_{12}}{|\gamma_{12}^1|}, \frac{Y_1^-}{\varepsilon_1^2}, \frac{Y_1^+}{\varepsilon_1^2}, \frac{Y_2^-}{\varepsilon_2^2}, \frac{Y_2^+}{\varepsilon_2^2}, \frac{Y_{12}}{|\gamma_{12}^2|} \right) \quad (4)$$

where ε and γ represent the normal and shear strains induced by unit shear force $N_{xy} = 1$, and Y is the maximum allowable strain. The superscripts on the strains represent the fibre directions of the layup ($[\theta_1/\theta_2]_{2s}$), and the superscripts of Y show tension, +, and compression, -. The subscripts 1 and 2 represent fibre and transverse directions, respectively. Each value used in this research is shown in Table 1. Note that all the strains in eq. (4) are the strains in the fibre and transverse direction of each ply. From eqs. (3) and (4), the maximum strain induced by the shear force, $\varepsilon_{x \max}$, is written as

Figure 2 Assembly process of CFRP cylinder. (a) conventional press-fit method, (b) proposed method using CFRP cylinder with atypical layup.

Figure 3 Coordinate system on CFRP cylinder.

$$\varepsilon_{x \max} = [A]^{-1}_{16} \cdot N_{xy \max} \quad (5)$$

Assuming that the x direction corresponds to the circumferential direction of the cylinder, the maximum strain in the circumferential direction is calculated by eq. (5).

Then the tension in the circumferential direction after releasing torque is calculated, which corresponds to the bottom image in Figure 2 (b). Assuming that the forces in the longitudinal and shear direction would be negligible after releasing torque, only the circumferential force, N_x in eq. (2) exists and eq. (2) reduces to

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A]^{-1}_{11} & [A]^{-1}_{12} & [A]^{-1}_{16} \\ [A]^{-1}_{12} & [A]^{-1}_{22} & [A]^{-1}_{26} \\ [A]^{-1}_{16} & [A]^{-1}_{26} & [A]^{-1}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Assuming no gap between the expanded cylinder and the core, $\varepsilon_{x \max}$ in eq. (5) corresponds to ε_x in eq. (6), leading to the circumferential force, N_x , after releasing torque as

$$N_x = \frac{\varepsilon_{x \max}}{[A]^{-1}_{11}} = \frac{[A]^{-1}_{16}}{[A]^{-1}_{11}} \cdot N_{xy \max} \quad (7)$$

The circumferential stress is obtained by dividing the circumferential force in eq. (7) by thickness of the cylinder, t , as

$$\sigma_x = \frac{N_x}{t} \quad (8)$$

Calculations were carried out for all sets of two fibre directions, θ_1 and θ_2 , with 1° increments from 0° to 90° .

2.3 Analysis Results

Figure 4 shows the strain, ε_x , calculated by eq. (3) with unit shear force (i.e., $N_{xy}=1$). The strain, ε_x , corresponds to the circumferential strain in the cylinder case. The horizontal and vertical axes represent fibre directions, θ_1 and θ_2 , respectively. The map has symmetrical contour, and several areas have high strain value above $30 \mu\epsilon$. Meanwhile, strain is not induced with harmonic layups (i.e., $\theta_2 = -\theta_1$ line in the figure), verifying the calculation.

Figure 5 (a) shows the maximum strain calculated by eq. (5). The maximum strain above 1.2% is

achievable. Note that though the areas with strain above 1.2% matches to the high strain area in Figure 4, the maximum strain are relatively low at the high strain area at the top right and bottom left in Figure 4. This would be because different criterions in eq. (4) were applied in different areas. Figure 5 (b) shows the stress after releasing torque calculated by eq. (8). The highest stress value is above 350 MPa at the vicinity of $\theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0^\circ$ where the fibres wound in the circumferential direction of the cylinder.

Figure 6 replots the relationship between the maximum strain (Eq. (5)) and stress after releasing torque (Eq. (8)). Each point represents a set of two fibre directions, θ_1 and θ_2 . Though the maximum strain exceeds 1.2% with some layups, the stress remains relatively low, below 200 MPa. The main purpose of this research is to achieve high tension (i.e., circumferential stress) to prevent the magnets from separating from the cores. Therefore, the layup circled in red in Figure 6 was chosen for the following experiment since the highest stress is expected. Note that though the maximum strain is 0.43%, which is about one third of the highest value with another layup (above 1.2%), the diameter expands by approximately 430 μm for a cylinder with a diameter of 100 mm, for example. Since the typical fitting tolerance between a cylinder and a column is about 100 μm , 430 μm is enough for insertion.

Table 1 Material properties used for theoretical analysis.

		Unit	Value
Elastic Property	Fiber direction, E_1	GPa	156
	Transverse direction, E_2	GPa	8.87
	Shear, G_{12}	GPa	4.67
	Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	-	0.34
Failure strain	Fiber direction/ Tension, Y_1^+	%	1.58
	Fiber direction/ Compression, Y_1^-	%	0.95
	Transverse direction/ Tension, Y_2^+	%	1.00
	Transverse direction/ Compression, Y_2^-	%	2.00
	Shear, Y_{12}	%	2.57

Figure 4 Circumferential strain, ϵ_x , induced by unit shear force (Eq. (3)).

(a)

(b)

Figure 5 Maximum strain and stress. (a) strain (Eq. (5)), (b) stress (Eq. (8)).

Figure 6 Maximum stress as a function of maximum strain.

3 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

3.1 Materials and Method

A CFRP cylinder having the designed layup was fabricated. The manufacturing method was sheet winding using prepreg with PAN-based carbon fibre. Considering thickness and fibre direction of the laminate, prepregs were cut into rectangular shapes. The prepregs were then wound around a steel carbon mandrel. Whole the prepregs and mandrel were covered with a breather and a vacuum bagging film. The sample was vacuumed and cured in an autoclave at a gauge pressure of 0.6 MPa. The cure process included 1°C/min heating and 170°C holding for 4 hours. Shape measurement of the cured cylinder verified that the cylinder was fabricated with the designed diameter and almost perfect circle in the cross-section.

The cylinder was then mounted on a torsion testing machine. Figure 7 (a) shows a photograph of the testing machine and the mounted cylinder. Four triaxial strain gauges were attached to the specimen, with two orthogonal axes of each gauge aligned with the coordinate axes shown in Figure 3. The gauges were positioned at the longitudinal centre of the specimen, corresponding to the four cardinal directions on its cross section. Figure 7 (b) illustrates a schematic of the cross-sectional view of the test setting. Test fixtures were used to connect the cylinder and testing equipment. The fixtures and the cylinder were adhesively jointed, and the fixtures and the testing equipment were pin-connected. Torsion was applied to the cylinder at a rotational speed of 0.5 deg/min until torque dropped. Strains measured by the attached strain gauges and torque were concurrently recorded every 0.1 second.

3.2 Experimental Results and Discussion

Figure 8 shows the measured strains as a function of applied torque. Figure 8 (a) is the result of strain measured by the gauges attached in 45° direction. The four values are almost consistent, confirming that the torque was appropriately applied. The circumferential strain (Figure 8 (b)) increased almost linearly with torque. The average value of the slope was 663 $\mu\epsilon$ /kNm, which is well consistent with the theoretical value (743 $\mu\epsilon$ /kNm), experimentally proving the anomalous Poisson's effect proposed in this research. The variations of the measured strains would be caused by variations during mounting on the test equipment. Figure 8 (c) depicts the longitudinal strain. The longitudinal strains at the SG1 and SG3 have different trend from that of the SG2 and SG4, which implies a bending moment was present during mounting.

Meanwhile, the maximum torque was about 0.7 kNm, which is less than half of the expected value. Sample observation after the test revealed that the drop in torque is likely to be caused by an adhesive

Figure 7 Test setup. (a) Photograph of setup, (b) Schematic of dotted red line in Figure (a).

Figure 8 Measured strains as a function of torque. (a) 45°, (b) Circumferential, (c) Longitudinal.

Figure 9 Photograph of edge area of CFRP cylinder after test.

failure between the test fixture and the cylinder, because no damage was observed in the cylinder (Figure 9). Though the bonding length was determined considering adhesive strength and applied torque, defects in the adhesion would have resulted in the failure. Mechanical joint is preferable to avoid process uncertainties commonly found in adhesive joints. However, with uniform cross section, the mechanically attached rigid fixture constrains deformation in the circumferential direction, preventing core insertion (Figure 10 (a)). Therefore, this research suggests a solution concept. This includes a CFRP cylinder with a tapered section where the grip fixture is attached (Figure 10 (b)). Although the attached area, similar to the uniform cross section, barely deforms, there is sufficient clearance between the core and the cylinder owing to the taper angle. Consequently, the core can be successfully inserted into the straight section of the cylinder without interaction. Future work will evaluate the validity of this proposed method.

4 CONCLUSION

This research aimed to propose a novel sleeve assembly method for SPM motors to reduce the cost and the press-fit pressure. The basic concept of the method is to use anisotropy of a CFRP and realize the 'anomalous Poisson's effect'. The effect induces normal strain by shear force. Theoretical analysis for the effect was carried out based on the classical lamination theory. The result led to a layup to maximize tension after the assembly while keeping enough clearance between the cylinder and core during assembly. Then a CFRP cylinder with the layup was fabricated to validate the theoretical analysis result and anomalous Poisson's effect. Torsion test was conducted with the cylinder and the circumferential strain increased with torque, successfully confirming the anomalous Poisson's effect. Furthermore, the strain increment with unit torque was $663 \mu\epsilon/\text{kNm}$, which is consistent with the theoretical value ($743 \mu\epsilon/\text{kNm}$). Additionally, a cylinder design with a tapered section was proposed to prevent the interaction between test fixture and the core during insertion, which was an issue found in the experiment. Future work will evaluate the validity of this method.

Cylinder with uniform diameter (Current work)

Cylinder with tapered section (Proposed)

Figure 10 Schematic of assembly methods.

(a) Cylinder with uniform diameter, (b) Cylinder with tapered section.

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